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**EMOTIONAL AND SPIRITUAL INTELLIGENCE WHY DOES IT MATTER FOR
TEACHERS ?**

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Abstract –

The present article explore the dimension of EQ and SQ with its composite elements and there implications in education psychologist and educationalist realized that IQ and EQ analysis are more effective if they are considered in the light of SQ.

Keywords: *Emotional intelligence, Spiritual intelligence*

In 1905 Alfred Binet and Theodore Simon developed the first modern intelligence test. Since that time we have been debating what “intelligence” is, where it comes from, and how to develop it ?

Our “Intelligence Quotient” or “IQ” is generally thought of as our analytical or mathematical intelligence and our linguistic intelligence (think of college entrance exams – verbal and math components). Initially it was expected that IQ would be a strong predictor of success in careers. In fact it has turned out to be a weak predictor of success. IQ appears to be related to minimum *standards* to enter a given a profession. Once we choose our career, what actually leads to success is far more complicated. Earlier it was believed that people with high IQ could alone become successful in personal, academic, family and professional life. Many people with high IQ may be productive and ambitious but found to be cold and detached. People with EQ, even with average IQ have found to be more successful because they are social, empathetic and cheerful. IQ is mostly determined by genetics and so it cannot be changed drastically. **But**

EQ is mostly learned and people can be trained. That's why a teacher should be educated about it.

What is Emotional Intelligence ?

According to Slovey & Mayer (1990) Emotional intelligence is a type of social intelligence that involves the ability to monitor one's own emotions, to discriminate among them and to use the information to guide one's thinking and actions.

According to Goleman – Hay/McBer research for success at the highest levels, in leadership positions, emotional competence accounts for virtually the entire advantage.

A Brief History of Emotional Intelligence

- 1930s – Edward Thorndike describes the concept of "social intelligence" as the ability to get along with other people.
- 1940s – David Wechsler suggests that affective components of intelligence may be essential to success in life.
- 1950s – Humanistic psychologists such as Abraham Maslow describe how people can build emotional strength.
- 1975 - Howard Gardner publishes *The Shattered Mind*, which introduces the concept of multiple intelligences.
- 1985 - Wayne Payne introduces the term emotional intelligence in his doctoral dissertation entitled "A study of emotion: developing emotional intelligence; self-integration; relating to fear, pain and desire (theory, structure of reality, problem-solving, contraction/expansion, and tuning in/coming out/letting go)."
- 1987 – In an article published in *Mensa Magazine*, **Keith Beasley** uses the term "emotional quotient." It has been suggested that this is the first published use of the term, although Reuven Bar-On claims to have used the term in an unpublished version of his graduate thesis.
- 1990 – Psychologists Peter Salovey and John Mayer publish their landmark article, "Emotional Intelligence," in the journal *Imagination, Cognition, and Personality*.

- 1995 - The concept of emotional intelligence is popularized after publication of psychologist and New York Times science writer Daniel Goleman's book Emotional Intelligence: Why It Can Matter More Than IQ.

Why is emotional intelligence (EQ) so important?

As we know, it's not the smartest people that are the most successful or the most fulfilled in life. We probably know that people who are academically brilliant and yet are socially inept and unsuccessful at work or in their personal relationships. Intellectual intelligence or IQ isn't enough on its own to be successful in life. IQ can help us get into college but it's EQ that will help us manage the stress and emotions of sitting our final exams.

Emotional intelligence affects:

1. Our performance at work.

Emotional intelligence can help us navigate the social complexities of the student-teacher interactions, lead and motivate others, and excel in our career. In fact, when it comes to gauging teachers, we should now view emotional intelligence as being as important as academic ability and should carry out EQ testing before hiring.

2. Our physical health.

If we are unable to manage our stress levels, it can lead to serious health problems. Uncontrolled stress can raise blood pressure, suppress the immune system, increase the risk of heart attack and stroke, contribute to infertility, and speed up the aging process. The first step to improving emotional intelligence is to learn how to relieve stress.

3. Our mental health.

Uncontrolled stress can also impact our mental health, making us vulnerable to anxiety and depression. If we are able to understand and manage our emotions, we will also be open to mood swings.

4. Our relationships.

By understanding our emotions and how to control them, we are better able to express how we feel and understand how others are feeling. This allows us to communicate more effectively and forge stronger relationships, both at work and in our personal life.

The Four Branches of Emotional Intelligence

Salovey and Mayer :

proposed a model that identified four different factors of emotional intelligence: the perception of emotion, the ability to reasoning using emotions, the ability to understand emotion and the ability to manage emotions.

Perceiving Emotions: The first step in understanding emotions is to accurately perceive them. In many cases, this might involve understanding nonverbal signals such as body language and facial expressions.

Reasoning with Emotions: The next step involves using emotions to promote thinking and cognitive activity. Emotions help prioritize what we pay attention and react to; we respond emotionally to things that garner our attention.

Understanding Emotions: The emotions that we perceive can carry a wide variety of meanings. If someone is expressing angry emotions, the observer must interpret the cause of their anger and what it might mean.

Managing Emotions: The ability to manage emotions effectively is a key part of emotional intelligence. Regulating emotions, responding appropriately and responding to the emotions of others are all important aspect of emotional management.

Table : 1 Five dimensions of Emotional intelligence

Dimension	Definition	Hallmarks
Self-Awareness	The ability to recognize and understand our moods, emotions and drives, as well as their effect on others	Self-confidence. Realistic self-assessment. Self-deprecating sense of humor.
Self-Regulation	The ability to control or redirect disruptive impulses and moods. The tendency to suspend judgment – to think before acting.	Trustworthiness and integrity. Comfort with ambiguity. Openness to change.
Motivation	A passion to work for reasons that go beyond money or status. A tendency to pursue goals with energy and persistence.	Strong drive to achieve Optimism, even in the face of failure. Organizational commitment.
Empathy	The ability to understand the emotional makeup of other people. Skill in treating people according to their emotional reactions	Expertise in building and retaining talented teachers. Cross-cultural sensitivity. Service to students and society.
Social skill	Proficiency in managing relationships and building networks. An ability to find common ground and build rapport	Effectiveness in leading change. Persuasiveness. Improved communication between students and teachers.

EQ is actually a large collection of skills. Goleman and Richard Boyatzis have recently grouped these skills into 4 quadrants.

Table : 2

Quadrants Of EQ Skills As Presented By Goleman And Richard Boyatzis

<p>SELF AWARENESS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emotional self-awareness. • Accurate self-assessment. • Self-confidence. 	<p>OTHER AWARENESS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Empathy. • Organizational Awareness. • Service Orientation.
<p>SELF MANAGEMENT</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emotional Self-Control. • Transparency. .(honest/trustworthy) • Adaptability. • Achievement orientation. • Initiative. • Optimism. 	<p>RELATIONSHIP SKILLS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing others. • Inspirational Leadership. • Influence. • Change catalyst. • Conflict management. • Teamwork and collaboration.

The research done by Goleman and Boyatzis shows that Self-Awareness skills must be developed before the others can develop. This makes sense if we consider Emotional Self-Awareness. If I don't know when I am angry how can I have Emotional Self Control? How can I have Empathy for your anger? How can I handle conflict appropriately? Research on EQ has left no doubt that these skills are vital for personal, educational and professional success for the students as well as for teachers. EQ is supplement to SQ. EQ & SQ are equally important for students and teachers. Emotional intelligence, when applied to the workplace, involves the capacity to effectively perceive, express, understand and manage emotions in a professional and effective manner at work (Palmer and Stough 2001)

What is Spiritual Intelligence ?

According to Emmons (2000) The adaptive use of spiritual information to facilitate everyday problem solving and goal attainment is as known as spiritual intelligence.

According to Wigglesworth (2002) Spiritual intelligence is the ability of individuals to behave with wisdom and compassion while maintaining inner and outer peace, regardless of the situation.

According to Stephen Covey (2004) Spiritual intelligence is the central and most fundamental of all the intelligences, because it becomes the sources of guidance for the others.

Five components of spiritual intelligence are as follows:-

1. The capacity to transcend the physical and material.
2. The ability to experience heightened states of consciousness.
3. The ability to sanctify everyday experience.
4. The ability to utilize spiritual resources to solve problems.
5. The capacity to be virtuous.

Spiritual intelligence is the set of abilities that individuals use to apply, manifest and embody spiritual resources, values and qualities in ways that enhances their daily functioning and well-being (Amram 2000).

On the analysis of five components mentioned above Wigglesworth (2002) have developed twenty one detailed skills of spiritual intelligence.

Table :- 3 The 21 Skills of Spiritual Intelligence (SQ)

<p>Higher Self/Ego self Awareness</p> <p>1. Awareness of own Worldview.</p> <p>2. Awareness of life purpose (mission).</p> <p>3. Awareness of values hierarchy.</p> <p>4. Complexity of inner thought.</p> <p>5. Awareness of Ego self / Higher Self .</p>	<p>Universal Awareness</p> <p>6. Awareness of interconnectedness of all life.</p> <p>7. Awareness of worldviews of others.</p> <p>8. Breadth of time / space perception.</p> <p>9. Awareness of limitations/power of human perception.</p> <p>10. Awareness of Spiritual laws.</p> <p>11. Experience of transcendent oneness.</p>
<p>Higher Self/Ego self Mastery</p> <p>12. Commitment to spiritual growth.</p> <p>13. Keeping Higher Self in charge.</p> <p>14. Living your purpose and values.</p> <p>15. Sustaining your faith.</p> <p>16. Seeking guidance from Spirit.</p>	<p>Social Mastery / Spiritual Presence</p> <p>17. A wise and effective spiritual teacher/mentor.</p> <p>18. A wise and effective change agent.</p> <p>19. Makes compassionate and wise decisions.</p> <p>20. A calming, healing presence.</p> <p>21. Being aligned with the ebb and flow of life.</p>

What is Inter-relationship between EQ and SQ ?

This simplest model describes four core intelligences. It shows a pyramid to demonstrate the simplest sequence of development. This is a very simple model which is helpful to imagine relation between development of child and development of intelligence (Wigglesworth 2006).

Vertical stacking display of multiple intelligences

The idea of this model is that as babies we first focus on controlling our bodies. Then our linguistic and conceptual skills develop (“IQ”) which are a key focus of our school work. We do some early development of relationship skills, but for many of us emotional intelligence (EQ”) becomes a focus area only later when we realize we need to improve – usually based on feedback in work relationships. spiritual intelligence (“SQ”) typically becomes a focus later – as we begin to search for meaning and ask “is this all there is?”

SQ and EQ are related to each other. I believe we need some basics of EQ to even successfully start our spiritual growth. Some degree of emotional self-awareness and empathy is an important foundation. Then, as our spiritual growth unfolds, there would be a strengthening of EQ skills – which would further reinforce and assist the growth of SQ skills.

Every teacher and student should have awareness about this Model and relation between EQ and SQ so that they can use this knowledge for the overall achievement in their life.

According to Wigglesworth (2002), the emotional abilities come earlier than spiritual abilities. Both of these abilities are related to each other and they strengthen each other. Spiritual intelligence increases an individual’s capacity to understand others at a higher level. Spiritual understanding allows an individual to discern both the 'true cause' of behaviour without judgment, and serve the 'true needs' of others until they themselves learn to meet their own

needs(The Economic Times 2010). This capacity is developed by first learning to free oneself from attachment and neediness and being able to meet our own inner needs. Being able to recognize, understand and respond to the emotions of others requires a level of emotional literacy that can only be developed by learning to recognize one's own feelings and emotions (self-awareness). This is the arena of emotional intelligence.

Importance of EQ and SQ for Teachers

Both Emotional Intelligence and Spiritual Intelligence refers to the inner most feelings or souls of the teachers/students. Both Emotional Intelligence and Spiritual have an impact on success. They improve performance, improve relations among co-workers and increase level of job satisfaction. It allows teachers/students to be motivated intrinsically rather than extrinsically. According to Katz and Kahn (1978), in terms of individual performance, main achievements are :-

1.In-role performance: Dependably meeting or exceeding standards of prescribed performance.

2.Extra-role performance: Innovatively and spontaneously going beyond prescribed roles to perform such actions as co-operating with others, offering suggestions for improvement and representing the organization favorably to outsiders.

Conclusion

Both Emotional Intelligence and Spiritual Intelligence touch the “nerve” of the Students as well as Teachers. It “makes” them to go beyond the normal actions. They complement each other. Both these intelligences are especially relevant in present era of materialism where values are receding to background. Hence, all the more reasons for its inculcation in teachers and students who will form future’s society.

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